

Original Article

STRATEGIC SKILLS NEEDED BY UNIVERSITY ENTREPRENEURSHIP EDUCATION STUDENTS FOR SELF-EMPLOYMENT AFTER GRADUATION IN ENUGU STATE

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17912988>

Abstract

This study was carried out to determine the strategic skills needed by University entrepreneurship Education students for self-employment after graduation in Enugu State. Descriptive survey research design was used for the study. Two research questions guided the study and two null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The population for the study comprised of 30 Business Educators from Federal and State Universities. There was no sampling because of the manageable size of the population. The instrument was a - 20 item structured questionnaire developed by the researchers entitled: Strategic Skills Needed by Entrepreneurship Education Questionnaire (SSNBEEQ). The instrument was duly validated by three experts. The reliability was done using Cronbach Alpha which yielded coefficient of 0.72 indicating that the instrument was reliable. Two research questions was answered using mean with standard deviations; while the null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using t-test at appropriate degree of freedom. Results of data analysis relating to the study have shown that innovative and adaptability skills respectively are needed by university entrepreneurship education students for self-employment after graduation in Enugu State. The null hypotheses tested showed that there was no significant difference in the mean scores of Business Educators in Federal and State Universities in Enugu State on innovative and adaptability skills respectively. Based on the findings, it was recommended that University Entrepreneurship Education students should be exposed to various innovative skills. Again, Business Educators should impact useful adaptability skills to her students.

Keywords: Strategic skills, University Entrepreneurship Education students, self-employment

Introduction

Entrepreneurship Education is one of the branches of Business Education in Nigeria Universities.

According to the core Curriculum and Minimum Academic Standards, CCMAS (2023), Entrepreneurship Education was introduced as an

integral part of Business Education along with Accounting, Marketing and Office Technology and Management (OTM). In essence, the OCMAS (2023) aims to promote Entrepreneurship Education as a tool for sustainable development recognizing its potential to empower individual and communities.

Entrepreneurship Education is a process of providing individuals with skills, knowledge and attitudes vital to become entrepreneurs and manage entrepreneurial ventures. According to Fayolle (2019), Entrepreneurship Education is a process of teaching and learning that aims to develop the entrepreneurial mindset, skills and knowledge vital for creating and managing entrepreneurial ventures as well as promoting entrepreneurship in various contexts. Moreover, Igwe (2019), opined that Entrepreneurship Education is an educational process that equips the recipients with the necessary competences to identify and exploit business opportunities and create and manage their own businesses. By incorporating Entrepreneurship Education into university curricula, it seeks to foster a culture of innovation, creativity and self-employment among university Entrepreneurship Education students.

University Entrepreneurship Education students are individuals who are pursuing academic programs or course that focus on developing the knowledge, skills and attitudes vital to become successful entrepreneurs. According to Kuratko (2017), Entrepreneurship Education students are those who are motivated to learn the principles of entrepreneurship, and are willing to apply this knowledge to start and run their own businesses. Therefore, such student should have innovative thinking, risk-taking, passion for business, desire for autonomy and willingness to learn. In Nigeria Universities, it is a four-year course for undergraduate programme. During this period, students are expected to acquire relevant skills that

will help them become self-employed after graduation.

A skill is a learned ability that allows someone to accomplish something successfully, whether it is a physical task, a mental activity or a combination of both. Skills are the practical activities which make one employable, self-reliant and relevant to the society (Oyinloye, Asonibare and Oluwalola, 2021). For University Entrepreneurship Education students to be self-employed after graduation; he or she need to acquire strategic skills while in school.

Strategic skills are the ability to develop, implement and evaluate plans and decisions that help achieve long-term goal and objectives. These skills involve analyzing complex situations, identifying patterns and relationships, and making reformed decisions that drive results. According to Hamel and Prahalad (2018), strategic skills involve the abilities to develop and implement strategies that drive innovation, growth and competitiveness. Moreover, strategic skills involve the abilities to think critically and creatively about the organization's future, and to develop plans and strategies to achieve its goals (Mintzberg, 2020). Entrepreneurship Education students particularly at the University level should acquire strategic skills especially innovative and adoptability skills while in the school. In this context, Innovative skills are a crucial component of strategic skills, as they enable individuals and organizations to develop new and creative solutions to complex problems. Duer, Gegensen and Christensen (2020) opined that innovative skills involve the abilities to discover, develop, and deliver new and innovative solutions that drive business growth. Innovative skills when acquire by the Entrepreneurship Education students will make them, stay ahead of the competition, drive growth, solve complex problems and enhance customer value.

Another strategic skill needed for self-employment by Entrepreneurship Education students is

adaptability skills. Aina (2019) noted that adaptability skills make one to adjust to changing circumstances, priorities and environments, and to respond effectively to new challenges and opportunities. Therefore, adaptability skills are critical for effective leadership, management and personal success. Adekunle (2020) noted that, adaptability skills make an entrepreneur to adjust to new situations, challenges, and opportunities, and to respond effectively to changing circumstances. Going by the Adekunle (2020)'s view, adaptability skills will make entrepreneurship Education students after graduation to adjust to new situations, learn from experiences, be open-minded, and maintain a positive attitude. Moreover, it will help them for self-employment.

Self-employment is a state of being one's own boss, making decisions about one's own business and bearing the financial risks and rewards. Shane (2019) opined that, self-employment is the act of creating and managing ones own business, often driven by entrepreneurial motivations and a desire for autonomy. In another development, Eya and Ugwunwoti (2022) posited that self-employment is the process of creating and managing one's own income, achieving personal fulfillment, and contributing to economic development. It is the responsibilities of the Entrepreneurship Educators (Business Educators) to impart into her students these strategic skills.

Business Educators according to Eya and Ugwunwoti (2022), are the implementers of curriculum and decides on what instructional materials to use, the methods to adopt, the amount of time to spend on each aspect and the equipment as well as space to use. Similarly, Ekoh-Nweke and Ezeabii (2021) opined that, Business Educator as an individual who has or obtained the professional qualifications which enables him or her to be employed to lecture or teach Business Education courses in any recognized tertiary institution in

Nigeria; that offer Business Education programme and is physically fit, of sound mind and mentally alert.

In Enugu State, Business Educators are employed by both Federal and State Universities. Federal universities are owned, financed and controlled by Federal Government (Agbo and Ugwunwoti, 2022). On the other hand, State Universities are owned, financed and controlled by State government. Despite the employment of these Business Educators, it seems that their products upon graduation; lack the needed strategic and skills to be self-employed. This is evidenced on the high rate of business failures in Enugu State owned by their graduates. Could it be that the skills taught to them are different from the ones needed to be self-employed? Or could it be that they were taught wrongly by the lecturers while in classroom? It is against this backdrop that this study on strategic skills needed by University Entrepreneurship Education students for self-employment in Enugu State was carried out.

Statement of the Problem

University Entrepreneurship Education (UEE) is a programme that teaches students to start and run their own business. Despite the growing importance of Entrepreneurship Education in Nigeria Universities, many graduates of this programme still struggle to establish and sustain successful businesses after graduation. This is particularly evident in Enugu State, where the rate of graduate unemployment and business failure remains high. One of the major challenges facing these graduates may be lack of strategic skills required to navigate the complex and dynamic business environment. Specifically, many Entrepreneurship Education students seem to lack the strategic skills needed to identify and capitalize on business opportunities. It is against this background that this work on strategic skills needed by university Entrepreneurship Education students was carried out.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to determine strategic skills needed by University Entrepreneurship Education students for self-employment after graduation in Enugu State.

Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Determine innovative skills needed by University Entrepreneurship Education students for self-employment after graduation in Enugu State.
2. Ascertain adaptability skills needed by University Entrepreneurship Education students for self-employment after graduation in Enugu State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What are the innovative skills needed by University Entrepreneurship Education students for self-employment after graduation in Enugu State?
2. What are the adaptability skills needed by University Entrepreneurship Education for self-employment after graduation in Enugu State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance at appropriate degree of freedom using t-test.

Ho1: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of Business Educators in Federal and State Universities respectively on innovative skills needed by University Entrepreneurship Education students for self-employment after graduation in Enugu State.

Ho2: Business Educators in Federal and State Universities in Enugu State did not differ significantly in their mean scores on adaptability skills needed by University Entrepreneurship Education students for self-employment after graduation.

Method

A descriptive survey research design was employed in the study. According to Nworgu (2015), descriptive survey is the one in which a group of people is studied by collecting and analyzing data

from few people considered to be representative of the entire group. The study was carried out in two government owned universities in Enugu State (University of Nigeria, Nsukka and Enugu State University of Science and Technology). The population for the study comprised of 124 Business Educators from University of Nigeria Nsukka and 6 from ESUT respectively totaling 30 Business Educators. There was no sampling because the population size was manageable.

The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire developed by the researchers entitled: Strategic skills needed by Entrepreneurship Education Questionnaire (ESSNBEQ). The instrument has three sections. Section A is on bio-data. Section B is on innovative skills and Section C contains items on adaptability skills. The rating responses were Very High Needed (VHN), Highly Needed (HN), Moderately Needed (MN) and Lowly Needed (LN) with numerical value of 4, 3, 2, and 1 respectively. The instrument was validated by three experts. Two from the Department of Business and Entrepreneurship Education and one from Department of Mathematics and Computer Education (Measurement and Evaluation) both from Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Enugu State. To test the reliability of the instrument, 20 Business Educators in government owned universities in Anambra State were used. Cronbach Alpha estimate was used to determine the internal consistency of the instrument, which yielded a coefficient index of 0.68; this index indicated that, the instrument was reliable enough to be used for the study.

The researchers with the help of the two research assistants used direct delivery techniques in the administration of the instrument to the respondents. At the end of the administration of the instrument, all the 30 copies were returned and used for the study; representing 100% rate of return. Mean with Standard deviation was used in answering the

research questions; while t-test was used in testing the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance at the appropriate degree of freedom. Decision rule for answering research questions was based on the real limits of the mean thus:

- Very High Needed 3.50 – 4.00
- Highly Needed 2.50 – 3.49
- Moderately Needed 1.50 – 2.49
- Lowly Needed 1.00 – 1.49

Table 1: Mean scores and standard deviation of Business Educators on the innovative skills needed by University Entrepreneurship Education students for self-employment.

S/N	Innovative skills include abilities to:	Federal n = 24		State n = 06		Overall n = 30		Decision
		\bar{X}_1	SD1	\bar{X}_2	SD2	\bar{X}	SD	
1.	Empathize with customers	3.60	0.58	3.59	0.60	3.60	0.59	HN
2.	Use digital tools to drive innovation	3.15	1.03	3.49	0.71	3.32	0.81	HN
3.	Collect, analyze and interpret data to inform innovative decisions	2.86	0.97	2.92	0.96	2.89	0.97	HN
4.	Generate valuable ideas that drive growth	3.20	0.79	3.12	0.82	3.16	0.81	HN
5.	Take calculated risks	3.26	0.83	3.26	0.85	3.26	0.84	HN
6.	Work with diverse stakeholders to co-create innovative solutions	3.23	0.83	3.35	0.59	3.29	0.63	HN
7.	Adapt quickly to changing technologies	3.48	0.50	3.47	0.60	3.48	0.53	HN
8.	Effectively communicate innovative ideas	3.49	0.71	3.15	1.03	3.32	0.89	HN
9.	Conduct experiments to test innovative prototypes	3.35	0.59	3.23	0.66	3.29	0.63	HN
10.	Stay up-to-date with latest trends	3.29	0.76	3.80	0.67	3.56	0.72	HN
	Cluster Mean (\bar{X})	3.29	0.76	3.34	0.75	3.32	0.74	HN

Data presented in Table 1 shows that mean scores of Business Educators in Federal and State Universities on items number 1 was very highly needed; while item numbers 2 to 10 with mean scores of 3.32, 2.89, 3.16, 3.26, 3.29, 3.48, 3.29 and 3.29 respectively were highly needed as innovative skills by University Entrepreneurship Education students for self-employment after graduation. The grand mean value of 3.56 also attested to that; while

For the hypotheses, when the calculated t-value was equal to or greater than the table value, the null hypotheses was rejected otherwise it was not rejected.

Results

Research Question 1

What are the innovative skills needed by University Entrepreneurship Education students for self-employment after graduation in Enugu State?

the cluster standard deviation of 0.72 shows the homogeneity of the opinion of the respondents.

Hypothesis I

There is no significant difference between the mean scores of Business Educators in Federal and State Universities respectively on innovative skills needed by University Entrepreneurship Education students for self-employment after graduation in Enugu State.

Table 2: Summary of t-test of difference between the Business Educators in Federal and State Universities on innovative skills needed by University Entrepreneurship Education students for self-employment after graduation in Enugu State.

Status	N	X	SD	Df	t-cal	t-table	Decision
Federal	24	3.29	0.76	28	0.36	1.96	N.S
State	06	3.80	0.67				
Total	30						

Table 2 shows that the calculated t-value at 0.05 level of significance and 28 degree of freedom is 0.36; while the table-value under the same condition is 1.96. Since the calculated t-value is less than the table value, the null hypothesis is therefore not significant. This means that there is no significant difference between the mean scores of Business Educators in Federal and State Universities on innovative skills needed by University Entrepreneurship Education students for self-employment after graduation in Enugu State.

Research Question 2

What are the adaptability skills needed by University Entrepreneurship Educatoors for self-employment after graduation in Enugu State?

Table

Table 3: Mean scores and deviation of Business Educators on adaptability skills needed by University Education students for self-employment after graduation in Enugu State.

S/N	Adaptability skills include abilities to:	Federal n = 24		State n = 06		Overall n = 30		Decision
		\bar{X}_1	SD1	\bar{X}_2	SD2	\bar{X}	SD	
11.	Adjust to changing circumstances	3.14	0.90	3.35	0.82	3.25	0.86	HN
12.	Bounce back from setbacks	3.58	0.84	3.45	0.87	3.52	0.71	HN
13.	Think critically in response to new situations	3.60	0.49	3.32	0.71	3.43	0.60	HN
14.	Quickly learn new technologies	3.41	0.68	3.32	0.72	3.40	0.70	HN
15.	Recognize alternative approaches	3.28	0.72	3.52	0.57	3.40	0.60	HN
16.	Manage others in adaptability to change	3.40	0.66	3.25	0.75	3.33	0.71	HN
17.	Prepare for changes rather than simply reacting to them	3.28	0.72	3.52	0.37	3.40	0.63	HN
18.	Operate effectively in unclear situations	3.25	0.75	3.40	0.66	3.32	0.71	HN
19.	Quickly adapt to new digital platforms	3.35	0.82	3.14	0.90	3.25	0.86	HN
20.	Work effectively in a rapidly changing environment with multiple priorities	3.60	0.49	3.32	0.71	3.43	0.16	HN
Cluster Mean (X)		3.41	0.68	3.27	0.76	3.42	0.76	HN

Data presented in Table 3 above shows that the mean scores of the respondents (Business Educators) on the item number 12 was very highly needed with the mean score of 3.52. The table also shows that the item numbers 11, 13, 14, 15, 16,17, 18, 19 and 20 respectively were highly needed as adaptability skills needed by University Entrepreneurship Education students for self-employment after graduation in Enugu State, with aggregate mean score ranges from 3.25 tp 3.43. The

Status	N	X	SD	Df	t-cal	t-table	Decision
Federal	24	3.41	0.68	28	0.194	1.96	N.S
State	06	3.27	0.76				
Total	30						

Table 4 shows that, the calculated t-value at 0.05 level of significance and 28 degree of freedom is 0.194; while the critical t-value under the same condition is 1.96. Since the calculated t-value is less than the table value, the null hypothesis is therefore not significant. This invariably means that, Business Educators in Federal and State Universities respectively in Enugu State did not differ significantly on adaptability skills needed by University Entrepreneurship Education students for self-employment after graduation/

Discussion of the Findings

The data presented in Table 1 showed that the respondents (Business Educators) from Federal and State Universities in Enugu State were in agreement that innovative skills are needed by University Entrepreneurship Education students for self-employment after graduation. These include abilities to empathize with customers, use digital tools to drive innovation, take calculated risks among others. The finding is in agreement with Christensen (2020) that, innovative skills gives ability to discover, develop and deliver new and innovative solutions that drive business growth.

grand mean of 3.42 also attested to that. The cluster standard deviation of 0.76 shows that the disparities of opinions of the respondents are slim.

Hypothesis 2

Ho2: Business Educators in Federal and State Universities in Enugu State did not differ significantly in their mean scores on adaptability skills needed by University Entrepreneurship Education students for self-employment after graduation.

The null hypothesis one tested on the innovative skills revealed that, there was no significant difference between the mean scores of Business Educators in Federal and State universities respectively on the innovative skills needed by University Entrepreneurship Education student needed for self-employment after graduation in Enugu State. The implication of the finding of no significant difference was that, the status of University had no significant influence in their opinions.

Data obtained regarding research questions two showed that, Business Educators in Federal and State Universities respectively were in harmony that; the itemized adaptability are keys for University Entrepreneurship Education students for self-employment after graduation in Enugu State. These skills are abilities to adjust to changing circumstances, bounce back from setbacks, and quickly learn new technologies among others. This is in agreement with Aina (2019) that, adaptability skills makes one to adjust to changing circumstances, priorities and environment and to respond effectively to new opportunities.

The null hypothesis two tested on the adaptability skills showed that, there was no significant difference between the mean scores of Business Educators in Federal and State Universities in Enugu State did not differ significantly in their mean scores on adaptability skills needed by University Entrepreneurship Education students for self-employment after graduation. The implication of the findings of no significant difference was that, the status of universities had no significant influence in their opinions.

Conclusion

Business Educators in Enugu State were of the view that innovative skills and adaptability skills are capable of making University Entrepreneurship Education students to be self-employed after graduation.

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- ### **Recommendations**
- Based on the findings and conclusion, the following recommendations were made:
1. University Entrepreneurship Education students should be exposed to various innovative skills for self-employment by Business Educators.
 2. Business Educators should impart useful adaptability skills to their students.
 3. Authority concern should be regular seminars to Business Educators on strategic skills.
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